

HISTORIA SCHOLASTICA

1/2019

Ročník / Volume 5

Praha / Prague 2019

EDITORIAL

Dear readers,

We are briefly introducing to you the first issue of *Historia scholastica* journal of the year 2019. Its main theme is bounded with the year 1918, because the last year we commemorated 100 years from essential political and social changes that incurred by the end of the World War I, when “disintegration of the old world” and seeking after the “new order” in the “new Europe” occurred.

The World War I, coupled with many expectations in the political and socio-cultural spheres, was to bring about a “resolution” of the then-perceived crisis of culture, society and the crisis of education. Efforts to social reform for a “new society” (often very diverse) have been evident in many socio-cultural areas at the turn of the century, and “Great War” had been linked to break the “old world” and enforcing a “new social order”. Since the last third of the 19th century there had been an intensification of the reform-pedagogical discussion that tried to reform “old school and upbringing”. At the same time, the “recipes” for the new education were very different. They depended on the personality concept of a pupil and a child, from which they were based or from which they developed.

These “recipes” also very often related to the broader socio-political background of pedagogical reformers. Reform education concepts oscillated between far-left, social-democratic, conservative Christian and conservative national “projects” to nationalistically closed or spiritually justified ideas. This, on one hand, dynamized the reform-oriented and socio-critical discussion, on the other hand, it did not detract from its basic instrumental foundations. This was supposed to bring “new models of school and education” that were not meant only for academic debates or bureaucratic-state “condemnation”, but they should become upbringing and educational concepts to be implemented.

The 1918 meant, not only for Central Europe, but also for the European and world situation, “rewriting” of the political distribution of Europe and the world, which also had a significant impact in the social sphere. The new states have sought to appropriate education models suitable for the situation after the global conflict and to take into account the continuity of social development in the newly emerged countries. It was not only a change of the boundaries or political arrangements of new states, but also a significant change in the “distribution of forces” in the discussion on the new goals of upbringing and education. It happened that the world that awakened from a “dark dream of war” into a new situation in which “a more democratic, socially more just order” was in a condition consisting of multinational, culturally and religiously diverse states.

The international issue of *Historia scholastica* journal deals with the following problems: how to understand the year 1918 in the context of European interwar discussions, understanding it as a milestone that gave the beginning to the „new“ arrangement of Europe, and when reconstructing the way how the questions about education were raised, we can understand it as a continuation of the pre-war pursuit to reform the education and society (Groppe, Hoffmann-Ocon, Grube and De Vincenti). We ask how such reforming concepts of education and society in the newly formed European states were constructed, including national, transnational, generally humanistic, political and religious arguments in discussion on educational models (Oelkers, Skiera, Göttlicher, Berner-Kurig). In the foreground of the interest stands as well the question of the transfer of European ideas about reform society to places „colonized“ by European ideas and culture (Depaepe).

Other contributions in this issue reconstruct the discussion of educational reform in individual European regions, to which less attention was dedicated in the historical-pedagogical research (Zorić, Miovska-Spaseva). We also ask how was discussed the question regarding the social emancipation as a goal of education, the role of the school in the social area and how development of girls' education and coeducation and also women's education was developed (Šušnjara).

Tomáš KASPER

Andreas HOFFMANN-OCON

Norbert GRUBE

Andrea DE VINCENTI

Markéta PÁNKOVÁ